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Willingness to pay to dive in the **Portofino** MPA

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This research forms part of the Green Bubbles RISE Project

Green Bubbles

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TOURISM RESEARCH IN ECONOMIC ENVIRONS AND SOCIETY

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1. Introduction

The Portofino marine protected area (MPA) extends around the promontory of the same name in the municipalities of Camogli, Portofino and Santa Margherita Ligure. The coast appears in all its charm: fascinating views and small inlets covered with vegetation bordering the sea. Along the southern side there are underwater cliffs reaching very deep levels where micro-habitats – rare for the Mediterranean area – originate.

Green Bubbles is dedicated to recreational scuba diving, an activity in which millions of people worldwide engage, yet that is poorly studied in the European context. Green Bubbles aims to maximise the benefits associated with diving while minimising its negative impacts, thus achieving the environmental, economic and social sustainability of the system with a specific focus on the European diving industry.

In order to fund conservation efforts in marine protected areas, researchers from TREES (as part of the Green Bubbles consortium) conducted a survey where a willingness-to-pay questionnaire (upper and lower bounded dichotomous choice questionnaire) was administered to assess the divers' attitude towards reef conservation and their willingness to pay for this, providing them with differing suggested amounts from which to choose a levy. The research process also involved interviews with the marine protected area management. The results of both these processes are described in this report.

2. Research aims

This research project had the following primary aims:

- To determine the divers' attitudes towards paying for reef conservation.
- To determine the aspects of the resources that the divers viewed as the most important, for instance good water quality, coastal development and reduction of sea bottom mortality.
- To determine the demographic profile of the divers.
- To determine the spending patterns of divers.
- To determine the aspects respondents regarded as the most important for an excellent diving experience.
- To determine the views of the MPA management concerning scuba tourism and their relationship with the diving operators.
- To make recommendations on the appropriateness and size of a levy for divers who enter the MPA and the management and implementation of such a system.

3. Method of research

To achieve these aims, the following approach was implemented: Firstly, a questionnaire was developed and administered by researchers from TREES at the North-West University in collaboration with the diving operators in Portofino. This survey took place from 22 June 2016 to 30 August 2016. The sampling areas where divers were surveyed included Santa Margherita, Rapallo and Recco. Respondents were approached and the aims of the study were explained. After they had given their consent, the questionnaires were handed to them for completion. A total of 442 completed questionnaires were returned.

Secondly, a qualitative approach was followed for an interview with the management of the MPA, conducted on 1 July 2016. The aim of the interview was to determine management's opinions regarding management issues identified from among the diving fraternity.

The results of this survey are discussed in the next section.

4. Profile of the diver respondents

Socio-demographic

4.1 Gender

As is shown in the figure, the majority of respondents were male (70,2%), while 29,82% were female.

4.2 Age

The majority of respondents were between 40 and 49 years (36%) old. The average age of the respondents was 42,08 years.

Age	%
< 30 years	16,9%
30 to 39 years	21,0%
40 to 49 years	36,0%
50 to 59 years	21,5%
60+ years	4,5%
Average age	42,08

DID YOU KNOW?

The average respondent was between **40 and 49 years** of age

4.3 Home language

The majority of respondents indicated that they were Italian speaking (88,9%), followed by 6,5% who spoke other languages, including French, Spanish, German, Austrian, Swedish, Portuguese and Japanese, and 4,6% who spoke English.

4.4 Country of origin

According to the table, the majority of respondents (89,6%) originated from Italy, followed by those who were from Switzerland (2,5%), France (1,5%), the UK (1,5%), Germany (1,3%), and from other countries including Argentina, South Africa, Poland, Norway, Austria, Japan, Peru and Sweden (3,5%).

Country	%
Italy	89,6%
Switzerland	2,5%
France	1,5%
UK	1,5%
Germany	1,3%
Other	3,5%

4.5 Level of education

The majority of respondents (34,7%) indicated that they had obtained a diploma qualification, followed by 30,1% who had a degree. The divers were therefore qualified people with high levels of education.

Level of education	%
High school	14,7%
Diploma	34,7%
Degree	30,1%
Postgraduate degree	17,0%
Other	3,5%

The majority of respondents had obtained a DIPLOMA qualification

4.6 Occupation

The largest groups of respondents (see the table below) in Portofino were in a professional or administrative occupation (25,1% and 25,1% respectively), followed by those who were dependents (10,7%). About 1,9% were unemployed and 0,9% were self-employed.

Occupation	%
Professional	25,1%
Administration	25,1%
Dependent	10,7%
Health	6,9%
Artist and design	5,3%
Management	3,1%
Education	2,5%
Unemployed	1,9%
Employed	0,9%

4.7 Marital status

The table below indicates that the largest group of the respondents was single (57,2%), followed by those who were married (38,3%). Those who were divorced, separated and living together accounted for 3,9%, 1,8%, and 0,6% respectively.

Marital status	%
Single	57,2%
Married	38,3%
Living together	0,6%
Divorced	3,9%
Separated	1,8%

4.8 Expenditure per person

Scuba dives were the category with the highest average spending (€79,85), followed by accommodation (€53,93), and diving courses and additional training (€48,49). The average total spending per group on their scuba diving trip was €339,00.

Spending on scuba diving trip	Amount
Scuba dives	€79,85
Diving courses and/or additional training	€48,49
Accommodation	€53,93
Transportation	€35,65
Shopping	€14,21
Food and beverages	€39,15
Diving insurance/renewal of diving credentials	€13,26
Buying new scuba diving equipment/gear	€38,05
Hiring new scuba diving equipment/gear	€3,27
Other activities (e.g. boat trips)	€3,93
Other expenses	€9,20

4.9 Length of stay in Portofino

The biggest group of respondents did not stay overnight (58,8%), while 30,8% stayed for 1 to 2 nights and 8,6% for 3 to 10 nights. On average, respondents stayed in the area for 1,23 nights.

Number of nights	2016
Did not overnight	58,8%
1 to 2 nights	30,8%
3 to 10 nights	8,6%
11+ nights	1,8%
Average	1,23 nights

4.10 Paying only for self

The highest percentage of respondents (39,6%) indicated that they were paying only for themselves during this trip, while 20,3% also paid for one other person. It was interesting to note that 29,7% of the respondents did not pay for themselves. This was perhaps because some had come in groups from a diving club and some had come in a family group and therefore one person had paid for the others.

People paid for	%
None	29,7
1 person	39,6
2 persons	20,3
3 persons	5,3
4 persons	3,2
5 persons	0,7
6+ persons	1,2
Average	1,40 people

4.11 Divers paid for

Of the people paid for in 4.9, almost half the respondents (41%) had paid for someone who was not diving, followed by 31,3% who were paying for a fellow diver and 20,4% for two additional divers.

People paid for	%
None	41,0%
1 person	31,3%
2 persons	20,4%
3 persons	3,5%
4 persons	1,6%
5 persons	0,9%
6+ persons	1,4%

4.12 Awareness of marine protected area

When respondents were asked to indicate whether they were aware that they were diving in an MPA, 98,8% indicated yes and only 1,2% indicated no.

MPA awareness	2016
Yes	98,8%
No	1,2%

4.13a Diving experience in Portofino

The largest group of attendees indicated that their diving experience at Portofino MPA was very good (45,8%), followed by 32,5% who indicated that it was excellent. Only 0,9% indicated that it was poor.

Rating	2016
Poor	0,9
Fair	1,4
Good	19,3
Very good	45,8
Excellent	32,5

4.13b Importance of user fee

The largest group of attendees indicated that user fees were somewhat important to the successful management of MPAs (50,4%), followed by 24,1% who indicated that they were moderately important. However, 5,2% indicated that user fees were not important at all.

Rating	%
Not at all important	5,2%
Slightly important	10,4%
Somewhat important	50,4%
Moderately important	24,1%
Extremely important	9,9%

4.13c Human behaviour causing the most damage

When asked which human behaviour caused the most damage to marine life, water pollution (83,1%) and commercial fishing (77,8%) were voted the most damaging. Diver’s impact on sea bottom mortality and marine life were voted the least damaging (9,7% and 8,5% respectively).

4.13d Willingness to pay

When asked about their willingness to pay user fees, 50% of the divers answered positively for the first bid at €5 per dive. Among those who were asked for €10 per dive as the first bid, 22,45% answered yes and 12,24% answered yes to the first bid at €15 per dive. The average willingness to pay was €7,03 per dive.

A more detailed analysis of the results using a double-bounded dichotomous contingent method and controlling for diving experience indicated that divers were willing to pay **€6,95**, and this was therefore the maximum levy per dive that could be charged. The results also showed that female divers were more likely to pay the higher amount in user fees than the male divers.

4.14 Number of visits

Exactly half the respondents (50%) indicated that they were diving at Portofino MPA for the first time, and the other half were diving there for either the second time or more.

Number of attendances	%
1st visit	50%
2nd time or more	50%

4.15 Years of diving

The majority of respondents (59,8%) indicated that they had been diving for 1 to 10 years. This was followed by 22,8% who had been diving for 11 to 20 years, and 12,3% for 21 to 30 years. The average respondent had been diving for 9,4 years.

Number of years	%
1 to 10 years	59,8%
11 to 20 years	22,8%
21 to 30 year	12,3%
41+ years	5,1%
Average	9,4 years

4.16 Number of dives logged

A little more than half the respondents (57%) indicated that they had logged between 1 and 100 dives. This was followed by 25,4% who had logged between 101 and 500 dives, and at least 10,1% who had logged more than 1 000 dives. The average respondent had logged 416 dives. This high average number of dives logged showed that most of the divers were experienced divers.

Number of dives	%
1 to 100 dives	57,0
101 to 500 dives	25,4
501 to 1 000 dives	7,5
1 001+ dives	10,1
Average	416 dives

4.17 Average number of dives logged per year

The majority of respondents (85,6%) indicated that they logged on average 1 to 50 dives per year. This was followed by 8,7% who logged between 51 and 100 dives per year. The average respondent logged 48,8 dives per year.

Dives logged per year	%
1 to 50 years	85,6
51 to 100 years	8,7
101 to 199 years	2,6
200+ years	3,2
Average	48,8

4.18 Portofino as a diving destination

The majority of respondents (90%) indicated that they definitely recommended Portofino as a diving destination.

Diving destination	2015
Yes	96,9%
No	3,1%

5. Results of the interview with MPA management

The MPA (marine protected area) is core to the marine tourism industry in Portofino. As research progressed regarding scuba diving in Portofino it came to light that there were several matters between the scuba diving fraternity (operators) and the management of the MPA in Portofino that needed to be addressed. Matters identified were the following:

- The first matter was that the diving fraternity in Portofino generated the most income for the MPA, but had the least input regarding the management of the MPA. At the time of the interview the diving fraternity had no representation on the MPA management board.
- The second matter was that at the time of the survey the different diving operators paid licence fees to the MPA to make use of the MPA. The suggestion was that fees paid to the MPA by diving operators must be paid directly to the MPA by the divers themselves.
- The third matter was that the fishing fraternity did not pay much to use the MPA, but there was a general feeling among diving operators that they had more political “weight” and that they tended to be less controlled than the diving fraternity.
- The fourth matter was that the services provided by the MPA to the diving fraternity were limited and questionable and needed to be addressed. The diving operators felt that the marketing of the MPA by the MPA management was limited and that the MPA could be better advertised.
- The final matter was that communication between the MPA and diving operators was limited and frustrating.

Based on these matters an interview was conducted with Valentina Cappanera and Giorgio Fanciulli during June 2016. Aspects of the interview are outlined below on the basis of questions developed by the researchers.

Question 1: MPA was asked to give some background regarding the MPA

The MPA starts from Santa Margherita and extends to Camogli to the west. It is about 3,7 km² in size. It is the third smallest MPA in Italy. In Italy there are now 27 MPAs. All diving needs to happen at the buoys and the diving centre needs to moor at the buoy. Anchors are forbidden. A maximum of 24 scuba divers per buoy are allowed at a given time (90 per day in total, although this figure is not really respected), although they can be transported by more than one boat. There are 22 diving buoys. Fishing is allowed at the buoys under certain regulations. Italian MPAs are all created by the

Ministry of the Environment, so they are state governed and funded by the government, with each MPA receiving different funding on the basis of a complex set of criteria of distribution.

Image 1: MPA Portofino

This image shows how the submerged environment is divided in the MPA. There is a prevalence of *Posidonia* in the C zone, while in the south front we have a coralligenous habitat with a rocky bottom, compared to the sandy bottom where *Posidonia* grows. These bottoms are the northernmost in the northern hemisphere where red coral can be found. The red coral is super protected and heavily studied also here in Portofino. From a scientific point of view this area is where the Italian marine biology was born.

Before the birth of the MPA the coral abundance cover and height were severely reduced due to human impact. Just before the arrival of the MPA the coral started to grow again and now there is a reported reduction in abundance but an increase in size, which is an accepted phenomenon (Bavestrello and Cattaneo). The governance is given to a local consortium, as is the case with all Italian MPAs. Our consortium is the three councils of Camogli, Santa Margherita and Portofino, the

Municipality of Genova and the University of Genova. I think we are the only Italian MPA with a university as part of the managing body.

Question 2: What are the sources of income for the MPA?

The annual budget is divided in different parts among the 27 (plus two archaeological parks) MPAs. The funding for the MPA received from 2008 to 2015 has decreased year by year. An additional €6 000 were allocated to the MPA for 2016. In total the MPA receive €160 000, plus additional external funding of about €40 000.

Question 3: How much income is generated from diving, fishing and other marine activities?

Income generated from fishing, mooring and diving permits contributes to the €160 000. From this money, 70% (about €100 000) comes from diving permits.

Question 4: How would you describe the communication between MPA and other role players such as diving operators and the fishing industry?

Management of the MPA indicated that communication between divers and fishers is not easy. It is not easy to collaborate. The reason is also cultural: the diving centres like to work on their own and were established long before the MPA. As for the fishers, the dialogue with them is difficult because of cultural reasons (because they have always used these areas for fishing and they do not accept that they can no longer do what they have always done, especially in Portofino and Camogli). The trust between fishing operators and the MPA is better.

With recreational fishing it is also difficult because the MPA would like fishing in the MPA to decrease and this generates conflict, but progress has been made. Communication between the diving centres (operators) is still a challenge, as the MPA did invite them to collaborate but the operators are less willing to cooperate.

Question 5: What is the MPA's view regarding charging a fee to the divers instead of to diving operators?

MPA management indicated that in the past there was a choice to pay for an authorisation and a ticket. Each diver had to pay €3 (buying a scratch ticket for every dive), or the operators could choose to pay a forfeit amount per boat during the year. They opted for the scratch ticket. As time progressed it was clear that the ticket system was not working due to the fact that people were cheating. This was cancelled and now each operator pays €1 500 per boat per year.

Three years ago the MPA discussed the possibility of an annual membership for the divers to be calculated on the number of divers coming here. Divers with membership can then dive, but the problem is to police this system. After numerous meetings no agreement could be reached. The MPA indicated that there should be an automated system to control the income, but it is difficult.

Question 6: What is the income generated from the diving fraternity used for?

Eighty percent of the income generated by the MPA is used to pay salaries, the rest is directed towards maintenance of the buoys, general maintenance and running costs of the offices. A small amount is spent on divulgation material like brochures and fliers. If the budget can improve, more can be directed to the marketing of the MPA.

Question 7: Tell us more about the fishing industry?

Currently there are 30 commercial fishers making use of the MPA. The average age of the owners is 57 years. The number of authorised boats is approximately 37 and there are cooperatives that have boats as well. No bottom trawling is allowed, only small-scale fishing such as lampara and tonnarella, which is a very old, traditional way of fishing.

Regarding commercial fishers, they do not pay anything to use the MPA. Residents (recreational fishers) have paid €50 per year since 2014. Non-residents (tourists) pay €157,30 for shore angling and €302,50 for boat angling per year.

It is difficult to monitor commercial fishing, and the MPA relies on their honesty to complete their log books with all the captures, and at the end of the year they need to hand these log books in. This assists in the monitoring of the MPA.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

This section provides an overview of the Portofino survey.

6.1 Profile of Portofino survey

The table below provides an overview of the profile of the divers in the Portofino marine protected area.

Demographic profile	
Gender	Male (70,2%)
Age	Average between 40 and 49 years
Home language	Italian (88,9%)
Occupation	Professional/administration (50,2%)
Level of education	Diploma (34,7%)
Consumer profile	
Highest average spending	Diving course/training (€112,07)
MPA awareness	Yes (98,8%)
Diving experience	Very good to excellent (78,3%)
Importance of user fee	50,4% indicated somewhat important
Willingness to pay	€6,95 per dive

From the results above scuba divers can be charged a maximum user fee of €7 per dive for access to the MPA. The amount can be lower, and we therefore recommend an amount of €5.

6.2 Conclusions and recommendations regarding MPA

From the interview with the management of the MPA the following conclusions were drawn:

- Most of the income of the MPA is generated from scuba divers. The total income generated by the MPA from fishing and diving is €160 000, of which 70% derives from diving.
- The fishing fraternity therefore pays the minimum to utilise the MPA.
- MPA management is supporting the idea that divers themselves must pay the fees to use the MPA and not the diving operators. However, a workable or implementable model needs to be found.
- Communication between the MPA and the diving fraternity is not of the best.
- 80% of total income generated by the MPA is spent on salaries.

The following recommendations were made:

- Diving operators must have representivity on the MPA board.
- Better communication platforms between the MPA and the diving fraternity and operators need to be developed.

Regarding the income-generating models for the MPA, three models were presented to the MPA.

Model 1: Current model (status quo)

The MPA and diving operators can continue making use of the current model. However, this model generates the least income for the MPA and therefore impacts on the sustainability of the MPA, as all over the world funding for conservation areas is decreasing.

Model 2: Conservation card

In Model 2 it is recommended that each diver must have an MPA conservation card for Portofino MPA. This card can, for example, be named the "BubbleCard" (or in Italian "BollaCarta"). The conservation card will function as follows:

- Each diver must purchase a conservation card (BubbleCard) from the MPA, diving operators or tourism information centres located in Ligure (for example in Portofino, Santa Margherita, Rapallo, Genova, Recco and Camogli). A minimum administration fee can be charged by the MPA for issuing the card.
- Information on the conservation card can be the following: name, ID number, diver's number, home address and photograph of diver.
- Divers can then upload any amount of euros on the card at pay zones or by EFT (internet banking).
- Electronic pay zones must then be established with the different diving operators. The diver simply needs to swipe the conservation card for each dive and the payment will be deducted from the card.
- The recommended cost per dive is a maximum of €5, based on the amount established above.
- Each transaction must then create a dive code (which will identify the diving operator, time of the dive, diver and date) that the divers must log in their diver's log book with each dive. The same dive code must be logged by the specific diving operator's system. Audits can then be performed by the MPA to verify dives logged by the operator to correspond with dives purchased by divers at the pay zone.
- The MPA can police diving operators' boats at different intervals to check payment by divers. If no proof can be presented, the diver as well as the diving operator can be fined.
- Two scenarios are provided for possible income that can be generated from the conservation fees system. First, 25 000 dives x €5 = €125 000 or 30 000 dives x €5 = €150 000. This amount is double the current amount generated by the current MPA system.
- A points system can be allocated to the conservation card. Divers can therefore accumulate points by using their conservation card. When a certain number of points have been accumulated, the points can be used for discount for diving-related gear or can translate into free dives.
- The card system will allow the MPA and diving operators to capture valuable information from the divers, such as their profile, diving behaviour and spending.

Model 3: Revival of previous ticket system

The MPA and diving operators can revive the previous ticket system, but with better policing. As this system was previously in use, the cost of reviving it would not be that expensive. It is recommended that the management/operation of the ticket system be contracted out to a management company. A certain percentage of the money generated for the MPA can then be paid to the management company as remuneration. Through this more income will be generated and the policing of payments will be done by an independent management company and not the MPA. This model also has the potential to generate more income than the current system if it is well managed. This will allow the MPA and diving operators to capture valuable information from the divers, such as their profile, diving behaviour and spending.